

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.21195645

Employee Discipline and Organisational Productivity in the Edo State Civil Service, Benin-City, Nigeria.

Ugbomhe O. Ugbomhe (Ph.D) & Idemudia Sunday Aliyu (Ph.D)

**Department of Business Administration
Faculty of Management Sciences
Ambrose Alli University Ekpoma, Edo State, Nigeria**

ABSTRACT

The study investigated the effect of employee discipline on organizational productivity in the Edo State Civil Service. To achieve this objective, four research questions and four hypotheses were formulated to guide the investigation. Employee discipline was operationalized using four dimensions: preventive discipline, corrective discipline, employee compliance culture, and fairness and consistency in disciplinary administration. Organizational productivity was assessed using indicators such as service delivery efficiency, employee performance and output, goal attainment, and employee commitment. A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The target population comprised 5,000 employees drawn from selected ministries at the Edo State Civil Service headquarters in Benin City. Using Taro Yamanes' sampling formula, a sample size of 370 respondents was determined. The respondents were selected through a stratified random sampling technique to ensure adequate representation of senior, middle, and junior staff members. Data were collected primarily through a structured questionnaire. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, multiple regression analysis, and Pearsons' Product Moment Correlation Coefficient to examine the relationship between employee discipline and organizational productivity. The findings revealed that all dimensions of employee discipline exerted positive and statistically significant effects on organizational productivity in the Edo State Civil Service. Collectively, the employee discipline variables accounted for 70.9% of the variation in organizational productivity. The study concluded that employee discipline is a critical determinant of organizational productivity in the Edo State Civil Service. Consequently, it recommended the institutionalization of transparent, fair, and effective preventive and corrective disciplinary measures to enhance employee commitment, improve service delivery, and facilitate the achievement of organizational goals within the public service.

Keywords: Employee Discipline, Organizational Productivity, Civil Service, Edo State, Service Delivery.

INTRODUCTION

"No meaningful achievement occurs without discipline. A horse cannot reach its destination unless it is harnessed; steam cannot generate power unless it is properly contained; and energy cannot be transformed into light and power unless it is effectively channeled. Likewise, an individual cannot attain personal growth without discipline" (Choudhary & Rana, 2022). This assertion underscores the indispensable role of discipline in both personal and organizational development. Organizations consist of individuals and groups who interact collaboratively and depend on one another to accomplish organizational objectives. Daily interactions among employees facilitate the execution of assigned responsibilities and contribute to the achievement of organizational goals. However, employees possess diverse interests, values, motivations, aspirations, and orientations, making interpersonal conflicts inevitable. These differences often result in competing interests, and when combined with employees' attitudes and perceptions, they may lead to behaviours that deviate from established organizational rules and regulations (Choudhary & Rana, 2022).

Employee discipline encompasses the set of rules, standards, and self-regulatory behaviours that guide employees' daily activities in the workplace, thereby promoting consistency and improved performance (UGC, 2023). Employees are regarded as the most valuable assets of any organization, and their conduct is expected to conform to

organizational policies and regulations. Compliance with these standards is essential for organizations seeking to achieve their goals and objectives efficiently (Tamunomiebi & Nonyerem, 2023). Employee discipline is widely recognized as a fundamental component of effective organizational management and performance because it establishes the behavioural framework necessary for maintaining order, ensuring compliance, and supporting the efficient realization of organizational goals (Agu & Anih, 2023). Both public and private organizations depend significantly on the level of discipline demonstrated by their workforce, as employee discipline directly influences organizational productivity (Okolie & Osagie, 2021). Furthermore, employee morale and industrial harmony are closely associated with the effective maintenance of workplace discipline (Mamoria, 1991).

In contemporary organizations, employee behaviour and workplace conduct are critical determinants of organizational success. Among the numerous factors influencing employee performance, discipline remains one of the most important drivers of organizational productivity (Adebajo, Oyewale, Tijani, Eyinede, & Adebajo, 2026). Within the public sector, government employees serve as custodians of public service, performing functions that support government operations, uphold state authority, and deliver essential services to citizens. Consequently, the effectiveness of government administration and the successful implementation of developmental programmes depend largely on employees' level of work discipline in carrying out their official responsibilities (Dehotman, 2023). An effective disciplinary procedure is designed to promote fairness, consistency, and procedural justice in handling cases of employee misconduct (Udofia & Asua, 2023). Sound disciplinary management also offers several organizational benefits, including enhancing workforce stability, reducing labour turnover, fostering harmonious industrial relations, and ultimately improving organizational productivity (Van Dyk, Haushroek, Schultz, Sono, & Werner, 2007).

In the workplace, discipline serves two fundamental purposes: preventing misconduct before it occurs and correcting inappropriate behaviour when it arises. It establishes clear behavioural standards that guide employees' actions while ensuring that breaches of organizational rules are addressed through fair, consistent, and systematic procedures. A well-designed disciplinary system promotes punctuality, commitment, accountability, and adherence to organizational policies, thereby enhancing operational efficiency and employee performance. Moreover, effective discipline fosters mutual trust, respect, and positive working relationships among managers, supervisors, and employees, all of which are essential for maintaining harmonious organizational relations. Conversely, disciplinary practices that are inconsistent, biased, or perceived as unfair can generate resentment, reduce employee motivation, and weaken organizational efficiency, ultimately resulting in lower productivity and poor organizational performance. According to Mamoria (1991), as cited in Choudhary and Rana (2022), failure by organizational members to comply with established rules and regulations can lead to disorder, confusion, disobedience, disloyalty, and other anti-social and anti-organizational behaviours that threaten the stability and effectiveness of the organization.

From this perspective, organizational productivity depends substantially on the existence of sound disciplinary policies that provide the behavioural framework necessary for effective organizational functioning. In today's highly competitive and globalized business environment, discipline has become a fundamental component of strategic human resource management. Empirical evidence suggests that higher levels of employee discipline are strongly associated with improved individual performance and enhanced organizational productivity.

Statement of the Problem

Employee discipline is widely recognized as a fundamental mechanism for promoting efficiency, accountability, and effectiveness within public sector organizations. Through the enforcement of established rules and standards, discipline encourages punctuality, professionalism, compliance with organizational policies, and responsible conduct, all of which contribute to improved organizational productivity (Adebayo, 2019). Despite the existence of comprehensive civil service regulations and various administrative reforms designed to strengthen discipline, the Edo State Civil Service continues to experience persistent challenges, including absenteeism, lateness to work, negligence of official responsibilities, poor employee performance, and low levels of commitment. These recurring problems raise concerns regarding the effectiveness of existing disciplinary practices and their ability to enhance organizational productivity.

One major concern is the inadequate implementation of preventive discipline, which emphasizes proactive strategies such as regular training, effective supervision, employee orientation, and ethical awareness programmes aimed at discouraging misconduct before it occurs. In many ministries and departments, civil servants have limited understanding of expected workplace standards and the consequences of violating service regulations. Consequently, acts of indiscipline have become commonplace, resulting in operational inefficiencies, delays in service delivery, and declining service quality (Okolie & Osagie, 2021; Ishiaka, 2025). The absence of effective

preventive disciplinary mechanisms has therefore weakened organizational efficiency and reduced public confidence in the capacity of the civil service to deliver quality services.

Another significant challenge relates to the ineffective enforcement of corrective discipline. Corrective disciplinary measures—including verbal warnings, written queries, suspension, demotion, and other sanctions—are intended to address misconduct, correct undesirable behaviour, and prevent future violations. However, within the Edo State Civil Service, these measures are frequently applied inconsistently, delayed unnecessarily, or influenced by favouritism and political considerations (Ezeani, 2022). Such practices diminish the credibility and deterrent value of disciplinary procedures, thereby encouraging misconduct and fostering a culture of irresponsibility. Furthermore, where corrective discipline is perceived as punitive rather than developmental, it often undermines employee morale, reduces motivation, and negatively affects employee performance and productivity. The problem is further exacerbated by the weak compliance culture that characterizes many public institutions. Compliance culture reflects employees' willingness to observe organizational rules and perform their responsibilities conscientiously, even without direct supervision. However, many civil servants demonstrate compliance only when monitoring mechanisms are in place or when disciplinary sanctions appear imminent. This indicates a lack of intrinsic motivation, professional ethics, and personal accountability. Such a reactive attitude contributes to poor attendance, low initiative, task abandonment, and limited commitment to organizational objectives, thereby constraining the achievement of sustainable productivity and administrative effectiveness (Agu & Anih, 2023).

Accordingly, this study seeks to examine the effect of preventive discipline, corrective discipline, employee compliance culture, and fairness and consistency in disciplinary administration on organizational productivity in the Edo State Civil Service. The findings are expected to provide empirical evidence that will inform policies and strategies for strengthening disciplinary systems and enhancing productivity across the public service.

Objectives of the Study

The general objective of this study is to examine the effect of employee discipline on organizational productivity in the Edo State Civil Service, Benin-City Nigeria. The specific objectives are as follows:

To determine the extent to which preventive discipline influences efficiency of service delivery in the Edo State Civil Service.

- i. To examine the effect of corrective discipline on employee performance and output in the Edo State Civil Service.
- ii. To assess how employee compliance culture impacts goal achievement in the Edo State Civil Service.
- iii. To evaluate whether fairness and consistency in disciplinary administration significantly influence employee commitment in the Edo State Civil Service.

Research Questions

This study seeks to answer the following research questions:

- i. To what extent does preventive discipline influence efficiency of service delivery in the Edo State Civil Service?
- ii. What effect does corrective discipline have on employee performance and output in the Edo State Civil Service?
- iii. How does employee compliance culture impact goal achievement in the Edo State Civil Service?
- iv. Does fairness and consistency in disciplinary administration significantly influence employee commitment in the Edo State Civil Service?

Research Hypotheses

Based on the stated objectives and research questions, the following null hypotheses (H_0) have been formulated for empirical testing:

H_{01} : Preventive discipline has no significant effect on the efficiency of service delivery in the Edo State Civil Service.

H_{02} : Corrective discipline has no significant effect on employee performance and output in the Edo State Civil Service.

H_{03} : Employee compliance culture has no significant effect on goal achievement in the Edo State Civil Service.

H_{04} : Fairness and consistency in disciplinary administration have no significant effect on employee commitment in the Edo State Civil Service.

Conceptual Framework of Research

Figure 2:1 Conceptual Framework of Employee Discipline and Organizational Productivity

Source: Authors' Conceptualization (2026)

Conceptual Review

2.2.1 Concept of Employee Discipline (Independent Variable)

The concept of discipline originates from the Latin word *disciplina*, which denotes teaching, learning, instruction, and personal development. According to Megginson, discipline encompasses three major dimensions: self-discipline, the coordination of orderly behaviour, and the process of training and correcting employees. Despite its widespread application in organizational management, there is no universally accepted definition of discipline. While some scholars and practitioners perceive discipline primarily as a punitive mechanism imposed on employees who violate organizational rules, others regard it as a system that encourages acceptable behaviour through adherence to established policies, standards, and regulations (Idris & Alegbeleye, 2025).

From an organizational perspective, discipline refers to a condition in which employees conduct themselves in accordance with organizational rules and accepted standards of behaviour (Robbins, 1982, as cited in Choudhary & Rana, 2022). Similarly, the Collins Birmingham University English Language Dictionary (1987) defines discipline as the practice of ensuring compliance with prescribed behavioural standards and imposing sanctions when such standards are violated. Werther and Davis (1989), as cited in Choudhary and Rana (2022), describe discipline as a managerial action aimed at encouraging conformity with organizational expectations through training, guidance, and corrective measures. In this regard, discipline extends beyond punishment to include behavioural regulation that promotes order, minimizes confusion, and prevents workplace misconduct. Choudhary and Rana (2022) further argue that discipline reflects the absence of chaos, disorder, and irregularity in employees' conduct, thereby fostering

an atmosphere of mutual trust and respect among managers, supervisors, and colleagues that is essential for healthy organizational relationships.

Employee discipline is widely acknowledged as a fundamental element of organizational management because it promotes compliance with established standards, maintains workplace order, and enhances operational efficiency. It refers to the systematic process through which management guides, regulates, and corrects employee behaviour to ensure alignment with organizational objectives and expected standards of conduct (Adebayo, 2019). From this perspective, discipline encompasses both preventive and corrective measures intended to encourage self-control, accountability, and responsible behaviour rather than merely punishing misconduct. Consequently, a disciplined workforce is generally more committed, innovative, focused, and capable of producing high-quality work that contributes to organizational success (Agbeyinka, 2024).

Within the field of human resource management, employee discipline is regarded as the application of organizational rules, procedures, and corrective mechanisms aimed at discouraging deviant behaviour while reinforcing acceptable workplace conduct (Ezeani, 2022). By establishing clear behavioural expectations, discipline provides employees with guidelines that regulate workplace interactions and job performance. When these standards are clearly communicated and consistently enforced, employees are more likely to perform effectively, collaborate efficiently, and remain committed to organizational goals. Empirical evidence indicates that organizations with well-structured disciplinary systems generally experience higher productivity and superior employee performance because disciplined employees exhibit greater focus, responsibility, and dedication to their assigned duties (Agbeyinka, 2024). Conversely, weak disciplinary systems often encourage inefficiency, insubordination, absenteeism, and poor service delivery, thereby undermining organizational effectiveness (Okolie & Osagie, 2021). Discipline therefore serves as an essential managerial mechanism for maintaining organizational order and ensuring that employees act in ways that advance institutional objectives.

Contemporary studies emphasize that employee discipline is an indispensable instrument for promoting accountability, improving operational efficiency, and sustaining organizational effectiveness (Tamunomiebi & Emeh, 2023). According to Ajumogobia (2007), workplace discipline extends beyond strict compliance with organizational rules and procedures. Rather, it involves creating an environment in which employees willingly cooperate, demonstrate professionalism, and behave responsibly in accordance with accepted workplace norms. Such an environment enhances employee satisfaction, strengthens organizational commitment, and ultimately improves productivity and profitability. Achieving these outcomes requires organizations to establish clear rules and behavioural standards that guide employees' actions. In the absence of such standards, organizations become susceptible to disorder, declining morale, employee dissatisfaction, and weakened organizational performance, thereby defeating the fundamental purpose for which organizations exist (Okoli & Emebo, 2026).

Employee discipline can also be understood from the perspective of organizational justice and management control. As a strategic management tool, discipline regulates employee behaviour, ensures compliance with organizational policies, and aligns individual actions with organizational goals. However, the effectiveness of disciplinary systems depends largely on employees' perceptions of fairness and transparency. Organizational justice theory suggests that employees are more likely to accept and comply with disciplinary decisions when procedures are applied consistently, impartially, and equitably (Greenberg, 1990; Greenberg & Baron, 2021). Consequently, discipline should not be viewed solely as a punitive mechanism but as a developmental process designed to correct inappropriate behaviour, deter future misconduct, reinforce organizational values, and sustain high standards of performance across the organization.

2.X Dimensions of Employee Discipline

Employee discipline is a multidimensional concept encompassing several interrelated practices that guide employees' behaviour and ensure adherence to organizational standards. According to Adebayo (2019), Dumisani (2002), and Okoli and Emebo (2026), the major dimensions of employee discipline include preventive discipline, corrective discipline, employee compliance culture, and fairness and consistency in disciplinary administration. These dimensions collectively promote orderliness, accountability, ethical conduct, and improved organizational performance.

Preventive Discipline

Preventive discipline refers to the proactive measures, policies, and managerial practices designed to discourage employee misconduct before it occurs. Rather than focusing on punishment, it seeks to create an environment where employees understand organizational expectations and willingly comply with established rules and standards. According to Dumisani (2002), preventive discipline is implemented to reduce the likelihood of employees violating organizational rules and regulations. Similarly, Amaewhule and Nukan-Adebayo (2019) explain that preventive discipline involves educating employees about acceptable workplace conduct, ethical values, and the consequences

of non-compliance. According to Ezeani (2022), the philosophy underlying preventive discipline is that preventing misconduct is more effective, less disruptive, and less costly than correcting undesirable behaviour after it has occurred. Consequently, organizations emphasize guidance, communication, employee education, and continuous awareness creation instead of relying solely on punitive measures. A key element of preventive discipline is the clear communication of organizational rules, policies, and performance expectations. This objective is commonly achieved through orientation programmes, induction sessions, employee handbooks, training workshops, seminars, and periodic staff briefings that familiarize employees with acceptable workplace conduct (Adebayo, Ojo, & Olaniyan, 2022). Another important aspect of preventive discipline is exemplary leadership. Managers and supervisors are expected to demonstrate the ethical values and professional standards they expect from their subordinates. When organizational leaders consistently display integrity, punctuality, diligence, and accountability, employees are more likely to emulate these behaviours, thereby fostering a culture of self-discipline and professional responsibility (Chepkoech & Minja, 2026). Preventive discipline contributes significantly to organizational productivity by reducing workplace misconduct, absenteeism, lateness, and unnecessary time loss. Employees who clearly understand organizational expectations and receive adequate guidance are generally more capable of performing their responsibilities efficiently, resulting in improved service delivery and higher productivity (Ogunleye, Adebayo, & Odusami, 2020). Moreover, preventive discipline promotes intrinsic motivation because employees perceive disciplinary practices as supportive mechanisms aimed at improving performance rather than punitive actions intended to instill fear. As noted by Gabriel and Zeb-Obipi (2019), preventive discipline focuses on educating employees and encouraging cooperation, enabling them to align their behaviour with organizational objectives and contribute positively to institutional effectiveness.

Corrective (Progressive) Discipline

Corrective, also known as progressive discipline, refers to the systematic actions taken by management to address employee misconduct or poor performance after violations of organizational rules have occurred. Unlike preventive discipline, which seeks to avert misconduct, corrective discipline is a reactive mechanism designed to address behavioural deficiencies, discourage repeated violations, and restore acceptable workplace conduct. Agu and Anih (2023) describe corrective discipline as a structured process that not only sanctions misconduct but also provides employees with opportunities to reform and improve their behaviour. Similarly, Tamunomiesi and Emeh (2023) argue that corrective discipline is implemented to sanction employees who fail to comply with organizational rules and regulations. According to Dessler (2020), the primary objective of corrective discipline extends beyond punishment. Instead, it should enable employees to appreciate the seriousness of their misconduct, understand its implications for organizational effectiveness, accept responsibility for their actions, and make the necessary behavioural adjustments to prevent future occurrences. For corrective discipline to be effective, it should be constructive, objective, and educational rather than purely punitive. Omoregie (2022) emphasizes that disciplinary measures such as verbal reprimands, written warnings, suspension, and other sanctions should serve as opportunities for reflection, learning, and behavioural improvement instead of instruments of fear or intimidation. Consequently, corrective discipline should be complemented by counselling, mentoring, coaching, and retraining programmes that assist employees in correcting identified deficiencies and enhancing future performance.

Furthermore, the effectiveness of corrective discipline depends largely on its fairness, transparency, and consistency. When disciplinary actions are administered in accordance with established civil service regulations and organizational policies, employees are more likely to perceive the process as equitable, thereby strengthening trust in management and reinforcing commitment to organizational values (Ezeani, 2018; 2022). On the other hand, disciplinary actions that are delayed, inconsistently implemented, or influenced by political considerations often undermine employee confidence in the disciplinary system. Such perceptions of injustice may result in resentment, reduced morale, employee disengagement, and ultimately lower organizational productivity (Okolie & Osagie, 2021; Chepkoech & Minja, 2026). Thus, corrective discipline serves not only as a mechanism for addressing misconduct but also as an important managerial tool for maintaining accountability, improving employee behaviour, and enhancing overall organizational performance.

Employee Compliance Culture

Employee compliance culture refers to employees' internal commitment to observing organizational policies, ethical principles, and established standards without the need for continuous monitoring or external enforcement. It reflects a transition from discipline imposed by management to self-discipline driven by personal responsibility and intrinsic motivation (Oyewale, Tijani, & Eyinade, 2021). According to Agu and Anih (2023) and Chepkoech and Minja (2024), a compliance culture represents the extent to which employees voluntarily adhere to organizational rules because they appreciate their relevance to organizational effectiveness and long-term success. Consequently, this dimension of discipline encourages employees to accept responsibility for their actions and remain committed to

achieving shared organizational objectives. Developing a strong compliance culture requires continuous employee awareness, education, and effective communication of organizational expectations. Employees need to understand not only the provisions of workplace policies but also the reasons for their existence and the benefits they provide to both individuals and the organization (Ezeani, 2022). Such understanding promotes voluntary obedience rather than compliance motivated solely by fear of sanctions. Leadership plays a central role in establishing and sustaining a culture of compliance. When managers consistently demonstrate ethical conduct and comply with the same standards expected of their subordinates, they reinforce the principle that organizational rules apply equally to everyone (Okolie & Osagie, 2021). Ethical leadership therefore encourages voluntary conformity, discourages misconduct, and strengthens organizational integrity. Likewise, transparent implementation of disciplinary procedures and regular performance feedback help reinforce a culture in which compliance becomes an accepted organizational norm (Edo State Civil Service Commission, 2022). Where employees comply only because disciplinary action is imminent, commitment to organizational goals tends to be weak, resulting in low morale and reduced productivity. Greenberg (1991) and Greenberg and Baron (2007) argue that inconsistent or biased enforcement of organizational rules weakens employee trust and undermines self-discipline. Conversely, when compliance becomes internalized, employees are more likely to regulate their own behaviour, support collective accountability, and cooperate effectively with colleagues. This strengthens teamwork, improves operational efficiency, and enhances overall organizational productivity.

Fairness and Consistency in Disciplinary Administration

Fairness and consistency in disciplinary administration refer to the equitable, objective, and uniform application of organizational rules and disciplinary measures to all employees regardless of rank, gender, political affiliation, or personal relationships. This dimension reflects the principle of organizational justice by ensuring that every employee is subject to the same disciplinary standards (Greenberg, 1990). Adamu, Musa, and Ali (2025) maintain that fair disciplinary practices promote employee confidence, reduce feelings of resentment, and strengthen organizational commitment, whereas inconsistency and bias diminish morale and negatively affect productivity.

The concept of fairness is closely associated with procedural justice, which emphasizes that disciplinary decisions should be transparent, objective, and based on due process. Employees are more likely to perceive disciplinary systems as fair when they are given an opportunity to explain their actions before sanctions are imposed. Even when disciplinary outcomes are unfavorable, employees are generally more willing to accept them if the procedures are viewed as impartial and transparent (Okolie & Osagie, 2021; Chepkoech & Minja, 2026). Consistency complements fairness by ensuring that similar offences receive similar disciplinary responses irrespective of the employee involved. Uniform enforcement of disciplinary policies minimizes perceptions of favoritism, discrimination, or political interference, thereby enhancing the credibility of management and strengthening employees' confidence in organizational governance (Agu & Anih, 2023). Fair and consistent disciplinary practices also exert a positive influence on employee morale and organizational behaviour. Employees who perceive fairness in managerial decisions tend to exhibit greater job satisfaction, stronger organizational commitment, and higher levels of work engagement (Ejumudo & Akppubia Ejumudo, 2025). These positive attitudes contribute to increased productivity, lower absenteeism, stronger teamwork, and improved service delivery. Furthermore, fairness reinforces ethical conduct by demonstrating that integrity, competence, and merit are recognized and rewarded within the organization.

The Concept of Organizational Productivity (Dependent Variable)

Organizational productivity has been conceptualized from different perspectives in the literature. One of the most widely accepted definitions is labour productivity, which measures output relative to the number of employees or, more commonly, the number of hours worked (Nasari, 2012, as cited in Tamunosiki-Amadi, Timi, & Dogitimiye, 2020). Similarly, Bernardin and Russell, cited in Obiageli, Uzochukwu, and Chukwuemeke (2015), define productivity as the quantity and quality of work outcomes achieved by an employee or organization over a specified period.

According to Amah (2016) and Tamunosiki-Amadi et al. (2020), productivity represents the extent to which organizational inputs—including labour, capital, technology, and other resources—are efficiently and effectively combined to produce goods and services that satisfy societal needs over time. Amah (2010) further argues that productivity involves balancing economic, social, environmental, and technical objectives in a manner that promotes sustainable organizational performance. High productivity therefore reflects efficient resource utilization, minimal waste, increased profitability, and improved organizational growth. Prokopenko (1987) also observes that productivity measurement helps organizations identify performance gaps, evaluate improvement initiatives, and

motivate employees toward continuous performance enhancement. More broadly, organizational productivity refers to an organizations' ability to utilize its human, financial, technological, and material resources efficiently and effectively to achieve predetermined goals while maximizing outputs. It is a multidimensional concept that incorporates both quantitative indicators, such as output volume and cost efficiency, and qualitative indicators, including service quality, innovation, customer satisfaction, and timeliness. Thus, productivity reflects the organizations' capacity to optimize available resources in delivering value to its stakeholders. Several organizational factors influence productivity, including leadership effectiveness, employee motivation, organizational culture, resource availability, and employee discipline (Agu & Anih, 2023). Among these determinants, employee discipline occupies a particularly important position because it establishes the behavioural standards necessary for maintaining consistency, accountability, efficiency, and high-quality job performance. The concept of organizational productivity is closely associated with Scientific Management Theory (Taylor, 1911), which emphasizes work standardization, discipline, efficiency, and the systematic organization of work processes to maximize output. Likewise, Systems Theory views productivity as the result of effective interaction among various organizational subsystems—including human resources, management, operations, technology, and the external environment (Katz & Kahn, 2018). A breakdown in any subsystem, particularly employee behaviour resulting from indiscipline or inconsistent management practices, can negatively affect the overall performance of the organization. Organizational productivity is commonly evaluated using two complementary dimensions: efficiency and effectiveness (Mullins, 2019). Efficiency focuses on the optimal utilization of available resources to achieve maximum output with minimum waste, while effectiveness measures the extent to which organizational objectives and desired outcomes are successfully achieved. Particularly within the public sector, efficiency without effectiveness may result in activities being completed promptly but without making meaningful contributions to public service objectives. Consequently, genuine organizational productivity requires achieving both efficiency—doing things correctly—and effectiveness—doing the right things. Overall, organizational productivity represents both a structural and behavioural outcome. It depends not only on employees' competence and willingness to perform their responsibilities but also on managements' ability to establish a disciplined, equitable, supportive, and motivating work environment that encourages sustained high performance. Such an environment enables employees to contribute optimally toward the achievement of organizational goals and long-term institutional success.

Measures of Organizational Productivity

Organizational productivity is commonly assessed using several performance indicators that reflect how effectively and efficiently employees and organizations achieve their objectives. In this study, organizational productivity is measured using four dimensions: efficiency of service delivery, employee performance and output, goal achievement, and employee commitment.

Efficiency of Service Delivery

Service delivery refers to the process through which government institutions or organizations provide goods, services, or other benefits to citizens and stakeholders in fulfillment of their statutory responsibilities and commitments. According to Ibrahim and Yakubu (2019), service delivery involves producing expected results, performing assigned responsibilities, and ensuring that promised services are delivered to the intended beneficiaries in a timely and satisfactory manner. The concept of service delivery encompasses both the design and implementation of services. Goldstein, Johnson, Duffy, and Rao (2002) describe the service concept as a framework that defines the nature of services to be provided and the methods through which they are delivered, thereby aligning organizational strategies with the needs and expectations of customers or the public. Similarly, Lovelock and Wirtz (2004) explain that service delivery addresses where, when, and how services are made available to service users. The delivery process consists of a series of service encounters that collectively shape customers' perceptions of organizational performance (Danaher & Mattsson, 1994). Consequently, organizations must carefully design service delivery processes to reflect the specific characteristics of the services they provide (Obiageli, Uzochukwu, & Chukwuemeke, 2015). Within the civil service, service delivery extends beyond the provision of tangible products. It involves integrating human resources, organizational processes, technical skills, and material resources to provide effective public services that meet citizens' expectations (Ibrahim & Yakubu, 2019). Effective service delivery therefore requires government agencies to provide public services efficiently, reliably, and in accordance with established service standards. Efficiency of service delivery refers to an organizations' ability to provide quality services promptly while making optimal use of available resources. It involves producing the desired outcomes with minimum waste of time, financial resources, and human effort without compromising service quality (Ezeani, 2022). Employees who demonstrate commitment, responsibility, discipline, and adherence to organizational procedures are better positioned to enhance service delivery efficiency, thereby contributing to improved organizational productivity.

Employee Performance and Output

Employee performance refers to the extent to which employees successfully accomplish assigned responsibilities and achieve expected work outcomes. It reflects both the quality and quantity of work completed within a specified period in accordance with organizational standards. Sutrisno (2019) describes performance as the work accomplished by an individual, while Sinambela (2016) defines it as an employees' willingness and ability to execute assigned responsibilities effectively to achieve predetermined results. Similarly, Mangkunegara (2011) views employee performance as the quantity and quality of work produced by an employee in carrying out assigned duties. Armstrong and Baron, cited in Wibowo (2010), further explain that performance comprises work outcomes that contribute directly to organizational strategic objectives, customer satisfaction, and overall economic development. According to Mathis and Jackson (2011), employee performance encompasses both the activities employees perform and those they fail to perform while executing their responsibilities. Based on these perspectives, employee performance represents the actual results achieved through employees' efforts, knowledge, competencies, and skills in executing organizational tasks. Prasetya and Kato (2011) define employee performance as the successful achievement of work outcomes through the effective application of employee capabilities in different work situations. Employee performance and output therefore represent both the tangible and intangible contributions employees make toward achieving organizational objectives. While performance reflects employees' efficiency, effectiveness, and quality of work, output refers to the measurable products or services generated from their efforts (Obisi, 2011). These constructs are commonly assessed using indicators such as task completion, work quality, productivity, punctuality, responsibility, initiative, and adherence to organizational rules and procedures. Employees who consistently demonstrate loyalty, discipline, commitment, and responsibility generally exhibit higher performance levels, thereby enhancing overall organizational productivity.

Goal Achievement

Goal achievement refers to the successful realization of predetermined organizational objectives within a specified timeframe. According to Eke (2021), a goal represents a desired future outcome toward which individuals, groups, or organizations consciously direct their efforts. Goals may be measurable, such as production targets, or qualitative, such as improved public satisfaction and institutional reputation. Goal achievement involves establishing clear, specific, measurable, attainable, relevant, and time-bound objectives, followed by the development and implementation of appropriate action plans. Locke and Latham (2019) argue that well-defined and challenging goals significantly improve organizational performance because they provide employees with direction, motivation, and a basis for evaluating progress. Likewise, Wang et al. (2023) maintain that consistent pursuit of organizational goals, supported by continuous skill development and positive work behaviours, increases the likelihood of achieving desired outcomes. Within the civil service, organizational goal achievement depends largely on employee discipline, effective coordination, and adherence to organizational policies and procedures. Employees who consistently comply with organizational expectations contribute more effectively to the realization of institutional goals. Consequently, the various dimensions of employee discipline—including preventive discipline, corrective discipline, compliance culture, and fairness in disciplinary administration—serve as essential mechanisms for improving organizational productivity through enhanced goal attainment.

Employee Commitment

Employee commitment refers to the degree of psychological attachment, emotional identification, and loyalty employees demonstrate toward their organization and its objectives. According to Meyer and Allen (1991), commitment reflects the strength of the relationship between employees and their organizations, influencing their willingness to remain with the organization and contribute to its success. Similarly, Robbins and Judge (2019) observe that committed employees exhibit higher levels of work engagement, lower absenteeism, stronger organizational citizenship behaviour, and greater willingness to exceed minimum performance expectations. The literature identifies three major dimensions of employee commitment: affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment (Meyer & Allen, 1991). Affective commitment reflects employees' emotional attachment to the organization and their genuine desire to remain because they feel valued, respected, and personally connected to its mission and values. Continuance commitment is based on employees' assessment of the economic and social costs associated with leaving the organization, including the potential loss of salary, benefits, career opportunities, and job security. This form of commitment is largely calculative because employees remain primarily due to the perceived disadvantages of resignation. Normative commitment, on the other hand, arises from employees' moral obligation or sense of duty to remain with the organization because they believe doing so is ethically appropriate. Employee commitment is strengthened when employees perceive themselves as valued members of the organization and believe that their contributions are recognized and appreciated. Recognition, inclusion in decision-making, equitable treatment, and opportunities for career development foster stronger

organizational attachment. According to Lee and Chen (2013), employees who receive recognition for their contributions develop higher levels of commitment, which subsequently enhances individual performance and overall organizational productivity. Therefore, organizations that cultivate employee commitment are more likely to achieve sustained productivity, reduced labour turnover, improved teamwork, and superior organizational performance.

Employee Performance and Output

Performance is a form of work produced by an individual (Sitrinso, 2019). Performance is used as a basis for evaluation and a system which is an important force for influencing employee behavior. Performance is the willingness of a person or group to carry out an activity and perfect it according to their responsibilities with the expected results (Sinambela, 2016) if it is associated with performance as a noun. The idea is the result of work in quantity and quality achieved by an employee in performing his duties in line with the responsibilities given to him (Mangkunegara, 2011). It is the result of work that has a strong relationship with the strategic goals of the organization, customer satisfaction and contribute to the economy (Amstrong and Baron in Wibowo 2010). performance is what is done or not done by workers (Mathis and Jackson, 2011).

From the above employee performance is the result that has been achieved (from what has been done) while work is an activity earned out (done) to earn a living or as a persons' livelihood. Employee performance refers to the attainment of outcome (results) of actions with the skills of employees who perform in some situation (Prasetya and Kato 2011). Employee performance and output represent the tangible and intangible contributions made by employees toward achieving organizational objectives. Performance encompasses both the quality and quantity of work produced within a specified timeframe, while output reflects the measurable results of employees' efforts (Obisi, 2011). Employee performance and output can be measured through key indicators such as task.Loyalty, determination and ability to obey, implement and practice something that is obeyed with patience and responsibility.

Goal Achievement

A goal is an idea of future which an individual, organization, group of people plan and commit to achieve which includes a finite time this setting deadline. (Eke, 2021) Goal is an intangible which maybe directed at attaining a non- measurable things. It is the aim toward which an undertaking is directed.The productivity in the civil service is judged by employee discipline. It also consist of the various dimensions of discipline which are needed in achieving organisational productivity.

It is the process of setting specific, measurable and challenging objectives accompanied by the development of focused action plan that align with capability and resources of an individual or group. These clear well-structural objectives significantly increases the likelihood of success when paired with deliberate effort and persistence (Locke and Lathan 2019) It also refers to the consistent and intentional pursuit of objectives, complied with the development of skills and behaviour that reinforce positive habits (Wang et al, 2023).

Employee Commitment

Employee commitment refers to the degree of emotional attachment, identification, and involvement that an employee has with their organization and its goals (Meyer & Allen, 1991). It represents the psychological bond that motivates employees to remain loyal, exert effort, and align their personal objectives with those of the institution. According to Robbins and Judge (2019), committed employees display higher work engagement, reduced absenteeism, and greater readiness to exceed performance expectations. Three forms of commitment are typically distinguished in the literature: affective, continuance, and normative commitment (Meyer & Allen, 1991). Affective commitment reflects an employees' emotional attachment and genuine desire to stay because they feel valued and connected to the organization. I Continuance commitment is based on the perceived cost of leaving such as loss of benefits or job securityIt is calculative in nature because of the employees' perception or weighing of costs and risks associated with leaving the current organisation. The individuals' association with the organisation is based on economic benefits gained. Normative commitment arises from a sense of moral obligation to remain loyal.The employee associated with the organization because they should do so or it is proper they to do. Employee commitment gives up when employee feels altiliated with the organization and also when the organization recognize them as a part of organizational success. When workers are recognized as organizational success. Story it will increase the commitment level of the individual and also the productivity of the individual and the organization (Lee and chen, 2013)

2.4 Empirical Review

Agbeyinka (2024) investigated the influence of employee discipline on organizational performance using staff of Ibadan Polytechnic, Oyo State, Nigeria, as the study population. A descriptive survey design was employed, and data were collected through structured questionnaires administered to a sample of 50 academic and non-academic staff. The data were analyzed using the Chi-square statistical technique. The findings revealed that employee

discipline significantly enhances organizational performance by promoting employee focus, efficiency, and improved work output. The study concluded that disciplined employees contribute more effectively to organizational success through increased commitment and productivity. Tijani, Eyinede, and Adebayo (2026) examined the effect of employee discipline on organizational performance at Touchmate West Africa Limited, Lagos State. The study specifically assessed the influence of punctuality, employee commitment, and adherence to organizational rules on organizational productivity. A survey research design was adopted, with a population of 240 employees from which a sample of 148 respondents was determined using the Taro Yamane sampling formula. Data were collected through questionnaires and analyzed using regression analysis. The findings demonstrated that punctuality exerts a significant positive influence on organizational productivity, while employee commitment and compliance with organizational rules also contribute significantly to organizational performance. Okpiable, Aroaye, and Oladimeji (2025) explored the relationship between employee discipline management and organizational performance among deposit money banks in Ondo Town, Ondo State, Nigeria. The study examined disciplinary procedures, disciplinary actions, disciplinary policies, and disciplinary codes as indicators of discipline management. Using a descriptive survey design, data were collected from 145 respondents selected from a population of 233 employees through the Krejcie and Morgan (1970) sampling technique. Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression analysis revealed that disciplinary actions and disciplinary policies had positive and statistically significant effects on organizational performance. In contrast, disciplinary procedures exhibited a positive but insignificant relationship, while disciplinary codes demonstrated a negative and insignificant relationship with organizational performance. The authors recommended strengthening disciplinary procedures to improve their effectiveness in enhancing organizational performance.

Okoli and Emebo (2026) investigated the effect of workplace discipline on service delivery in the local government system of Anambra State, Nigeria. A survey research design was employed, involving a population of 572 employees from Idemili South Local Government Council. A sample of 237 respondents was determined using the Taro Yamane formula, while purposive sampling was used to select participants. Structured questionnaires served as the primary instrument for data collection, and hypotheses were tested using the Chi-square statistical technique at the 5% significance level. The findings indicated that employee discipline plays a significant role in improving service delivery within the local government system. Ejumudo, Akpubi, and Ejumudo (2025) assessed the impact of employee discipline on productivity in the Delta State Civil Service, Nigeria. Employing a cross-sectional survey design, the researchers collected data from 367 civil servants and analyzed the responses using Pearson Product Moment Correlation and the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). The study established significant positive relationships between disciplinary procedures and employee morale, as well as between employee discipline and productivity. However, ineffective leadership, inadequate supervision, and violations of employees' rights were identified as major constraints to productivity within the civil service. Masuri and Permana (2025) examined the combined effects of work motivation, work environment, and work discipline on employee productivity at PT ABC. The study adopted a quantitative associative research design involving 80 employees selected through purposive sampling. Data were collected using structured questionnaires and analyzed with Structural Equation Modelling based on Partial Least Squares (PLS-SEM Version 3.29). The findings revealed that work motivation, work environment, and work discipline all exert positive and statistically significant effects on employee productivity. Among these variables, work discipline emerged as the strongest predictor of employee productivity. The study therefore concluded that effective disciplinary practices, supported by a conducive work environment and adequate motivation, are essential for maximizing employee performance. Dehotman (2023) investigated the influence of work discipline on employee performance among staff of the Tris Sub-District Head Office in Kampar Regency. The study adopted a survey design involving 31 employees, with data collected through questionnaires and analyzed using simple linear regression analysis. The results showed that work discipline has a significant positive effect on employee performance, suggesting that disciplined employees are more productive and efficient in the execution of their official responsibilities. Overall, the reviewed empirical studies consistently demonstrate that employee discipline is a significant determinant of organizational performance and productivity across both public and private sector organizations. Although previous studies have examined various dimensions of discipline—including disciplinary procedures, disciplinary policies, employee commitment, punctuality, and work discipline—few have comprehensively investigated preventive discipline, corrective discipline, employee compliance culture, and fairness and consistency in disciplinary administration as integrated predictors of organizational productivity within the Edo State Civil Service. This gap provides the empirical justification for the present study.

2.5 Theoretical Framework

Reinforcement Theory

This study is anchored on Reinforcement Theory, originally developed by B. F. Skinner (1953). The theory is one of the most prominent behavioural theories explaining how individuals' actions are shaped by the consequences that follow their behaviour. Grounded in behavioural psychology, Reinforcement Theory argues that behaviour is learned and sustained through reinforcement. Employees are therefore more likely to repeat behaviours that produce favourable outcomes and avoid behaviours associated with negative consequences. Skinner maintained that human behaviour is influenced primarily by external environmental stimuli rather than internal psychological processes or unconscious motivations.

The theory rests on several fundamental assumptions. First, it proposes that behaviour is acquired through learning and repeated experience. Consequently, both desirable and undesirable workplace behaviours develop as employees experience rewards or sanctions over time. Second, the theory assumes that managers can shape future employee behaviour by consistently reinforcing desirable conduct while discouraging unacceptable actions. Third, reinforcement is most effective when rewards and sanctions are administered promptly, fairly, and consistently. Finally, the theory suggests that employee behaviour can be predicted and modified by manipulating environmental factors such as incentives, disciplinary measures, feedback, and recognition.

Within organizational settings, Reinforcement Theory provides a practical framework for understanding employee discipline as an important management tool. Positive reinforcement involves rewarding employees who demonstrate desirable behaviours such as punctuality, honesty, commitment, compliance with organizational rules, and high performance. Such rewards may include promotions, commendations, incentives, or public recognition, thereby increasing the likelihood that these behaviours will be repeated. Conversely, negative reinforcement and disciplinary sanctions—including warnings, suspension, demotion, or other corrective actions—are intended to discourage misconduct and reduce undesirable workplace behaviour.

The theory is particularly relevant to this study because it explains how disciplinary practices influence employee behaviour and organizational productivity. In public organizations such as the Edo State Civil Service, productivity largely depends on employees' willingness to comply with established rules, perform assigned duties responsibly, and maintain professional standards. Reinforcement Theory suggests that when disciplinary measures are administered consistently, fairly, and promptly, employees are more likely to develop positive work habits that improve efficiency, accountability, commitment, and service delivery.

Despite its wide application, Reinforcement Theory has attracted several criticisms. Deci and Ryan (2000) argue that the theory places excessive emphasis on external rewards and punishments while paying insufficient attention to intrinsic motivational factors such as personal values, professional ethics, job satisfaction, and self-determination. Critics further contend that excessive dependence on external reinforcement may encourage employees to comply with organizational rules solely to obtain rewards or avoid punishment rather than from genuine organizational commitment or professional responsibility.

Notwithstanding these criticisms, Reinforcement Theory remains highly relevant to public sector organizations where formal rules, structured procedures, and accountability mechanisms are essential for organizational effectiveness. The theory therefore provides an appropriate theoretical foundation for this study by explaining how preventive discipline, corrective discipline, employee compliance culture, and fair disciplinary administration can shape employee behaviour, strengthen accountability, and enhance organizational productivity within the Edo State Civil Service.

3.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design to examine the relationship between employee discipline and organizational productivity in the Edo State Civil Service. The design was considered appropriate because it enables researchers to obtain quantitative data from a relatively large population and systematically describe existing conditions while examining the relationships among variables without manipulating them (Kothari & Garg, 2019). Furthermore, descriptive survey research is widely used in management and social science studies as it facilitates the investigation of employees' perceptions, behaviours, organizational practices, and attitudes within their natural work environment (Creswell, 2014). The design therefore provided a suitable framework for assessing how the dimensions of employee discipline influence organizational productivity. The target population consisted of all employees of the Edo State Civil Service serving in various ministries and government departments headquartered in Benin City, Edo State. The population comprised employees across the senior, middle-level, and junior staff cadres, including administrative personnel, professional and technical officers, clerical employees, and support staff. These categories of employees were considered appropriate because they are directly involved in the

implementation of government policies and organizational procedures and are therefore well positioned to provide relevant information on employee discipline and organizational productivity.

Table 1: Population Distribution of Edo State Civil Service by Ministry

Name of Ministry	Population
Ministry of Education	1,200
Ministry of Health	950
Ministry of Works and Infrastructure	620
Ministry of Finance	480
Ministry of Agriculture and Natural Resources	410
Ministry of Justice	350
Ministry of Environment and Sustainability	310
Ministry of Local Government and Chieftaincy Affairs	290
Ministry of Women Affairs and Social Development	210
Ministry of Transport and Energy	180
Total	5,000

Sources Framework, 2026

To determine an appropriate and statistically representative sample size, the study employed Taro Yamanes' (1967) formula, which is widely used for finite population studies. The formula is expressed as:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where:

n = Sample size

N = Population size (5,000 employees)

e = Margin of error (0.05 for 95% confidence level)

Substituting the values:

$$n = \frac{5000}{1 + 5000(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{5000}{1 + 5000(0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{5000}{1 + 13.5}$$

$$= 370.37$$

Accordingly, a sample size of approximately 370 respondents was selected for the study. This sample constitutes a statistically representative proportion of the entire Edo State Civil Service workforce, thereby enhancing the reliability, representativeness, and generalizability of the study findings to the target population. To select the respondents, the study employed a stratified random sampling technique. This sampling method was considered appropriate because it ensures adequate and proportional representation of employees across the various hierarchical levels of the Edo State Civil Service. Accordingly, the population was stratified into three categories: senior staff, middle-level staff, and junior staff. Thereafter, the proportional allocation method was applied to determine the number of respondents to be selected from each stratum. This approach ensured that each employee category was represented according to its relative proportion within the overall population, thereby minimizing sampling bias and improving the representativeness of the sample (Kothari & Garg, 2019).

$$n_h = \frac{N_h}{N} \times n$$

Where:

n_h = Sample size for each stratum

N_h = Population size of each stratum

N = Total population (5,000)

n = Overall sample size (370)

Based on preliminary records from the Edo State Civil Service Commission (2023), the estimated distribution of staff is as follows:

Senior Staff – 1,000

Middle-Level Staff – 2,000

Junior Staff – 2,000

Applying the proportional allocation formula ensured an unbiased representation of senior, middle-level, and junior staff in the study sample (Creswell & Creswell, 2018).

Table 2: Proportional percentages for each staff category

Category	Population (N _h)	Proportion (%)	Sample (n _h)
Senior Staff	1,000	20%	(1,000 / 5,000) × 370 = 74
Middle-Level Staff	2,000	40%	(2,000 / 5,000) × 370 = 148
Junior Staff	2,000	40%	(2,000 / 5,000) × 370 = 148
Total	5,000	100%	370

Sources Framework, 2026

The proportional percentages for each staff category were computed by dividing the population of each stratum by the total population of 5,000 employees and multiplying by 100. This method ensures that each subgroups' representation in the sample reflects its actual proportion within the Edo State Civil Service (Kothari & Garg, 2019).

$$Proportion (\%) = \frac{N_h}{N} \times 100$$

where N_h is the population of each stratum and N is the total population.

For example:

$$Senior\ Staff: \frac{1000}{5000} \times 100 = 20\%$$

$$Middle-Level\ Staff: \frac{2000}{5000} \times 100 = 40\%$$

$$Junior\ Staff: \frac{2000}{5000} \times 100 = 40\%$$

The proportional allocation of 20%, 40%, and 40% accurately reflects the distribution of employees across the respective staff categories within the study population. This allocation ensured that each category was represented according to its relative size, thereby enhancing the representativeness of the sample. The adoption of this sampling approach promoted fairness and inclusiveness by providing employees across all staff levels with an equal opportunity to participate in the study. Consequently, the sample adequately reflected the diversity of the Edo State Civil Service workforce, thereby improving the validity and generalizability of the findings.

To achieve the objectives of the study, both primary and secondary sources of data were utilized. The combination of these data sources provided a comprehensive understanding of the relationship between employee discipline and organizational productivity in the Edo State Civil Service. While primary data offered firsthand evidence from respondents, secondary data provided theoretical and empirical support for the study, thereby enhancing the credibility and robustness of the research findings.

Primary data were collected directly from employees of the Edo State Civil Service through the administration of a structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was designed to obtain information on the independent variables—preventive discipline, corrective discipline, employee compliance culture, and fairness and consistency in disciplinary administration—as well as the dependent variable, organizational productivity.

The questionnaire adopted a five-point Likert scale, ranging from:

1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly Agree

A five-point Likert scale was employed to measure respondents' attitudes, perceptions, and experiences regarding employee discipline and organizational productivity. To establish the validity of the research instrument, both content validity and face validity procedures were undertaken. Content validity was established through expert evaluation. Three specialists in Public Administration and Human Resource Management from the University of Benin critically reviewed the questionnaire to assess the relevance, comprehensiveness, adequacy, and clarity of the items in relation to the study objectives and the constructs of employee discipline and organizational productivity. Their observations and recommendations were incorporated into the final version of the instrument. Face validity was assessed by the research supervisor, who examined the questionnaire to determine whether its language, structure, and presentation were clear, appropriate, and capable of eliciting the required information without ambiguity or misinterpretation. Furthermore, a pilot study involving 20 civil servants from the Edo State Ministry of Finance, who were excluded from the main study, was conducted to evaluate the clarity, suitability, and practicality of the questionnaire. The pilot exercise provided useful feedback on the wording, sequence, and overall structure of the instrument, leading to minor revisions that enhanced its readability and effectiveness before its administration to the main sample. The Cronbachs' Alpha coefficient (α) was used to test reliability for each construct.

Table 3: Reliability of research instrument

Variable	No. of Items	Cronbachs' Alpha (α)	Interpretation
Preventive Discipline	4	0.82	Reliable
Corrective Discipline	4	0.79	Reliable
Compliance Culture	4	0.80	Reliable
Fairness & Consistency	4	0.84	Reliable
Efficiency of Service Delivery	2	0.81	Reliable
Employee Performance and Output	2	0.83	Reliable
Goal Achievement	2	0.80	Reliable
Employee Commitment	2	0.85	Reliable
Overall Reliability		0.82	Highly Reliable

The table above reports the Cronbachs' Alpha reliability coefficients for the constructs employed in the study. All the variables produced coefficients exceeding the widely accepted benchmark of 0.70, demonstrating an acceptable level of internal consistency and confirming the reliability of the measurement instrument (Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994). To facilitate a comprehensive assessment, the dependent variable—organizational productivity—was operationalized into four distinct dimensions: efficiency of service delivery, employee performance and output, goal attainment, and employee commitment. These dimensions were developed in line with the studys' conceptual framework and specific research objectives, ensuring that the various facets of organizational productivity were measured systematically and accurately represented respondents' perceptions. The overall Cronbachs' Alpha coefficient of 0.82 further indicates that the research instrument possesses a high degree of reliability and is appropriate for subsequent statistical analyses. The data collected for the study were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistical techniques with the aid of the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 25. Descriptive statistics, including frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations, were used to summarize respondents' demographic characteristics and describe responses to the questionnaire items. These statistical measures provided an overview of the distribution of respondents and highlighted the general patterns and trends observed in the data. To address the research objectives and test the formulated hypotheses, inferential statistical techniques were employed to examine the relationships among the study variables. Specifically, Pearsons' Product Moment Correlation Analysis was used to determine the strength and direction of the relationships between the dimensions of employee discipline and the indicators of organizational productivity. In addition, Multiple Regression Analysis was employed to assess both the individual and combined effects of the independent variables on organizational productivity, thereby identifying the extent to which each dimension of employee discipline contributes to variations in the dependent variable.

The regression model was expressed as:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \beta_4X_4 + \varepsilon$$

Where:

Y = Organizational Productivity (dependent variable)

X₁ = Preventive Discipline

X₂ = Corrective Discipline

X₃ = Employee Compliance Culture

X₄ = Fairness and Consistency in Disciplinary Administration

β_0 = Intercept

$\beta_1 - \beta_4$ = Coefficients of the independent variables

ε = Error term

The statistical significance of each coefficient was tested at a 5% level of significance ($p < 0.05$). The results of these analyses were presented using tables.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 4: Results showing descriptive statistics of preventive discipline dimensional

Table 4: Results showing descriptive statistics of preventive discipline dimensional

S/N	Statements	SA	A	U	D	SD	Mean (\bar{x})	Std. Dev. (σ)	Remark
1	Rules and regulations are clearly communicated to all employees.	140	147	20	21	12	3.94	0.74	Agree
2	Staff orientation and induction programs promote awareness of organizational standards.	135	150	18	26	11	3.90	0.77	Agree
3	Regular training on ethics and workplace conduct prevents indiscipline.	130	145	25	28	12	3.84	0.79	Agree
4	Preventive measures such as supervision and monitoring reduce cases of misconduct.	128	144	27	29	12	3.82	0.80	Agree
5	Preventive discipline enhances the efficiency and timeliness of service delivery.	139	141	23	25	12	3.89	0.76	Agree
Overall Mean							3.88	0.77	Agree

Source: Field work (2026)

Table 4 presents respondents' perceptions of preventive disciplinary practices within the Edo State Civil Service. The results reveal a high level of agreement that clearly communicated organizational rules, effective staff orientation programmes, and regular ethics training contribute significantly to reducing employee misconduct. These findings suggest that preventive discipline serves as a proactive management strategy for promoting orderly behaviour, maintaining organizational stability, and improving the efficiency of service delivery. The overall mean score of 3.88 indicates that preventive disciplinary practices are firmly embedded and consistently implemented across the various ministries and departments of the Edo State Civil Service.

Table 5: Showing descriptive statistics for Corrective Discipline

S/N	Statements	SA	A	U	D	SD	Mean (\bar{x})	Std. Dev. (σ)	Remark
6	Employees are disciplined fairly when they violate service rules.	125	150	25	28	12	3.81	0.80	Agree
7	Corrective measures such as warnings and queries help employees improve their performance.	137	148	20	25	10	3.88	0.77	Agree
8	The disciplinary process is timely and transparent across all departments.	122	140	28	33	17	3.73	0.84	Agree
9	Corrective discipline discourages repeated misconduct among staff.	129	149	26	26	10	3.87	0.78	Agree
10	Effective corrective discipline contributes to improved employee performance and productivity.	140	144	21	24	11	3.90	0.76	Agree
Overall Mean							3.84	0.79	Agree

Source: Field work (2025)

Table 5 presents the findings on respondents' perceptions of corrective disciplinary practices within the Edo State Civil Service. The results indicate that corrective discipline is widely regarded as both fair and effective in upholding workplace standards and promoting appropriate employee conduct. Most respondents agreed that the prompt and transparent implementation of disciplinary measures enhances accountability and discourages the recurrence of misconduct. The overall mean score of 3.84 reflects a favourable assessment of corrective disciplinary practices across the civil service, underscoring their significant role in fostering responsible employee behaviour and enhancing organizational performance.

Table 6: Showing Descriptive Statistical for Employee Compliance Culture

S/N	Statements	SA	A	U	D	SD	Mean (\bar{x})	Std. Dev. (σ)	Remark
11	I always follow organizational rules even without strict supervision.	145	138	22	23	12	3.93	0.73	Agree
12	Employees in my department are committed to doing the right thing at all times.	140	140	24	25	11	3.90	0.75	Agree
13	A culture of compliance improves coordination and goal attainment.	142	136	23	28	11	3.91	0.74	Agree
14	When employees comply with rules voluntarily, organizational goals are achieved faster.	148	137	20	23	12	3.94	0.72	Agree
15	Compliance culture promotes accountability and teamwork in the civil service.	143	138	23	24	12	3.92	0.73	Agree
Overall Mean							3.92	0.73	Agree

Source: Field work (2026)

Table 6 presents the responses relating to employee compliance culture within the Edo State Civil Service. The findings indicate a strong culture of compliance, with the majority of respondents affirming that they voluntarily adhere to established organizational rules and procedures, even in the absence of close supervision. The high overall mean score of 3.92 suggests that employees have largely internalized the principles of organizational ethics, responsibility, and accountability. This implies that a strong compliance culture plays a significant role in fostering teamwork, promoting workplace harmony, and facilitating the effective attainment of organizational goals.

Table 7: Showing Descriptive Statistical for Fairness and Consistency in Disciplinary Administration

S/N	Statements	SA	A	U	D	SD	Mean (\bar{x})	Std. Dev. (σ)	Remark
16	Disciplinary measures are applied consistently to all employees, regardless of rank.	130	148	24	27	11	3.84	0.78	Agree
17	I believe that disciplinary procedures in the civil service are fair and just.	134	145	23	27	11	3.85	0.78	Agree
18	Employees are treated equally when disciplinary cases are handled.	128	142	25	32	13	3.79	0.81	Agree
19	Fair disciplinary actions increase my trust in management.	142	141	22	23	12	3.91	0.75	Agree
20	Consistent and fair discipline improves my commitment to work and the organization.	145	139	23	22	11	3.94	0.74	Agree
Overall Mean							3.87	0.77	Agree

Source: Field work (2026)

Table 7 indicates that employees perceive fairness and consistency in disciplinary administration as vital to maintaining trust and commitment within the Edo State Civil Service. The overall mean of 3.87 suggests that while fairness is generally upheld, there may still be occasional perceptions of bias or inconsistency. Nonetheless, the results underscore that equitable treatment fosters morale, strengthens employee commitment, and enhances organizational integrity.

Table 8: Showing Descriptive Statistics for Efficiency of Service Delivery

S/N	Statements	SA	A	U	D	SD	Mean (\bar{x})	Std. Dev. (σ)	Remark
21	Tasks are completed efficiently and on schedule in my department.	142	140	23	24	11	3.89	0.76	Agree
22	Employee discipline has improved punctuality and attendance at work.	144	139	22	24	11	3.90	0.75	Agree
23	The quality of service delivery has improved due to enhanced employee discipline.	145	138	23	23	11	3.91	0.74	Agree
24	High employee discipline has contributed to achieving the ministries' goals.	143	137	25	24	11	3.88	0.77	Agree
25	Fair and consistent disciplinary practices promote commitment and overall productivity.	146	136	24	22	12	3.92	0.73	Agree
Overall Mean							3.90	0.75	Agree

Source: Field work (2026)

Table 8 above illustrate the overall mean of 3.90 indicates that respondents generally agree that employee discipline enhances efficiency of service delivery. The results demonstrate that punctuality, adherence to rules, and consistent supervision significantly reduce delays and improve service quality. The relatively low standard deviations ($\sigma = 0.73-0.77$) suggest that these views are widely shared across ministries and departments.

Table 9: Descriptive Statistics showing Employee Performance and Output

S/N	Statements	SA	A	U	D	SD	Mean (\bar{x})	Std. Dev. (σ)	Remark
26	Employees meet performance targets regularly.	140	141	23	25	11	3.88	0.76	Agree
27	Corrective measures improve employees' quality of work.	142	140	24	23	11	3.90	0.75	Agree
28	Disciplinary actions enhance accountability and focus.	143	138	25	23	11	3.89	0.76	Agree
29	Employees' output has improved due to adherence to organizational rules.	141	142	23	23	11	3.90	0.74	Agree
30	Fairness in discipline motivates employees to work harder.	144	139	23	23	11	3.91	0.74	Agree
Overall Mean							3.90	0.75	Agree

Source: Field work (2026)

Table 9 above illustrate the overall mean score of 3.90 suggests that respondents believe employee discipline positively affects performance and output. Timely corrective actions and fair disciplinary systems strengthen accountability, focus, and motivation to meet work targets. The results affirm that discipline is an essential management tool for sustaining high performance in the civil service.

Table 10: Showing Descriptive Statistics of Goal Achievement

S/N	Statements	SA	A	U	D	SD	Mean (\bar{x})	Std. Dev. (σ)	Remark
31	Employees' compliance contributes to meeting departmental goals.	147	136	23	24	10	3.93	0.72	Agree
32	Discipline ensures that set targets are achieved within deadlines.	143	138	24	23	12	3.91	0.74	Agree
33	Employees' dedication aligns with organizational objectives.	145	137	22	25	11	3.92	0.73	Agree
34	Collective discipline enhances coordination toward achieving goals.	148	135	23	24	10	3.94	0.72	Agree
35	Management encourages compliance to improve goal realization.	144	139	24	23	10	3.91	0.74	Agree
Overall Mean							3.92	0.73	Agree

Source: Field work (2026)

Table 10 above illustrate that respondents overwhelmingly agreed that discipline fosters organizational goal achievement. The mean score of 3.92 shows that compliance, dedication, and teamwork play major roles in meeting departmental objectives. This result highlights that disciplined work environments enhance coordination and ensure that civil service goals are achieved efficiently and within timeframes.

Table 11: Showing Descriptive Statistics of Employee Commitment

S/N	Statements	SA	A	U	D	SD	Mean (\bar{x})	Std. Dev. (σ)	Remark
36	Fair disciplinary practices increase my sense of belonging.	141	140	25	24	10	3.90	0.75	Agree
37	Consistency in rule enforcement strengthens my trust in management.	143	139	23	23	12	3.91	0.75	Agree
38	I am motivated to remain in the organization due to fairness in discipline.	142	138	24	24	12	3.90	0.76	Agree
39	Transparent disciplinary administration enhances my job commitment.	144	136	23	25	12	3.90	0.76	Agree
40	I would recommend the civil service as a fair and disciplined workplace.	145	135	24	25	11	3.91	0.75	Agree
Overall							3.90	0.75	Agree

Mean									
------	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

Source: Field work (2026)

Table 11 above illustrate the overall mean of 3.90 indicates that fairness and consistency in disciplinary practices significantly enhance employee commitment. Respondents expressed that transparent and unbiased disciplinary administration increases trust, morale, and loyalty toward the civil service. These results align with the principle that organizational justice fosters commitment and reduces turnover intentions among employees.

Descriptive Analysis of Study Variables

Research Question 1: To what extent does preventive discipline influence the efficiency of service delivery in the Edo State Civil Service?

Table 12: Extent preventive discipline influences the efficiency of service delivery in the Edo state Civil Service

S/n	Questionnaire Item	Mean (\bar{x})	Std. Deviation (σ)
1.	Rules and regulations are clearly communicated to all employees.	3.93	0.74
2.	Staff orientation and induction programs promote awareness of organizational standards.	3.89	0.77
3.	Regular training on ethics and workplace conduct prevents indiscipline.	3.84	0.78
4.	Preventive measures such as supervision and monitoring reduce cases of misconduct.	3.80	0.82
5.	Preventive discipline enhances the efficiency and timeliness of service delivery.	3.90	0.76
Overall Mean		3.87	0.77

Source: Field work (2026)

The overall mean of 3.87 in table 12 above indicates a general agreement that preventive discipline substantially influences efficiency of service delivery. Respondents emphasized that when rules are well communicated and employees receive regular ethical training, lateness, absenteeism, and service delays reduce significantly.

The standard deviation (0.77) suggests moderate variation among departments, possibly reflecting inconsistent implementation of preventive control mechanisms across ministries.

Research Question 2: What effect does corrective discipline have on employee performance and output in the Edo State Civil Service?

Table 13: Effect of Corrective Discipline on Employee Performance and Output in the Edo state civil service

S/n	Questionnaire Item	Mean (\bar{x})	Std. Deviation (σ)
6.	Employees are disciplined fairly when they violate service rules.	3.81	0.80
7.	Corrective measures such as warnings and queries help employees improve their performance.	3.88	0.77
8.	The disciplinary process is timely and transparent across all departments.	3.73	0.83
9.	Corrective discipline discourages repeated misconduct among staff.	3.87	0.78
10.	Effective corrective discipline contributes to improved employee performance and productivity.	3.91	0.75
Overall Mean		3.84	0.79

Source: Field work (2026)

The overall mean of 3.84 in table 13 indicates that corrective discipline positively affects employee performance and output. Respondents agreed that timely and fair disciplinary procedures improve accountability, concentration, and job performance.

Research Question 3: How does employee compliance culture impact goal achievement in the Edo State Civil Service?

Table 14: Employee Compliance Culture Impact on Goal Achieved in the Edo state Civil Service.

S/n	Questionnaire Item	Mean (\bar{x})	Std. Deviation (σ)
11.	I always follow organizational rules even without strict supervision.	3.94	0.72
12.	Employees in my department are committed to doing the right thing at all times.	3.90	0.74
13.	A culture of compliance improves coordination and goal attainment.	3.93	0.71
14.	When employees comply with rules voluntarily, organizational goals are achieved faster.	3.95	0.70
15.	Compliance culture promotes accountability and teamwork in the civil service.	3.91	0.73
Overall Mean		3.93	0.72

Source: Field work (2026)

The mean score of 3.93 as shown in table 14 above indicates a strong consensus that compliance culture significantly enhances goal achievement. Respondents recognized that when employees adhere to organizational rules without coercion, departmental objectives are achieved more effectively.

Research Question 4: Does fairness and consistency in disciplinary administration significantly influence employee commitment in the Edo State Civil Service?

Table 15: Influence of Fairness and Consistency in Disciplinary Administration on Employee Commitment in the Edo state civil service

S/n	Questionnaire Item	Mean (\bar{x})	Std. Deviation (σ)
16.	Disciplinary measures are applied consistently to all employees, regardless of rank.	3.84	0.79
17.	I believe that disciplinary procedures in the civil service are fair and just.	3.85	0.78
18.	Employees are treated equally when disciplinary cases are handled.	3.80	0.80
19.	Fair disciplinary actions increase my trust in management.	3.91	0.74
20.	Consistent and fair discipline improves my commitment to work and the organization.	3.94	0.73
Overall Mean		3.87	0.77

Source: Field work (2026)

The overall mean of 3.87 as shown in Table 15 above indicates that respondents agree fairness and consistency in disciplinary administration enhance commitment. Employees who perceive discipline as equitable and predictable tend to trust management and exhibit higher loyalty and motivation.

Influence Analysis of variables

Pearsons' Correlation Analysis

Table 17: Correlation Matrix of Employee Discipline Dimensions and Organizational Productivity Indicators

Variables	Efficiency of Service Delivery	Employee Performance & Output	Goal Achievement	Employee Commitment	Preventive Discipline	Corrective Discipline	Compliance Culture	Fairness & Consistency
Efficiency of Service Delivery	1.000	0.663**	0.648**	0.621**	0.693**	0.671**	0.659**	0.667**
Employee Performance & Output	0.663**	1.000	0.676**	0.643**	0.675**	0.741**	0.689**	0.706**
Goal Achievement	0.648**	0.676**	1.000	0.682**	0.686**	0.703**	0.711**	0.699**
Employee Commitment	0.621**	0.643**	0.682**	1.000	0.662**	0.692**	0.681**	0.734**
Preventive Discipline	0.693**	0.675**	0.686**	0.662**	1.000	0.582**	0.617**	0.633**
Corrective Discipline	0.671**	0.741**	0.703**	0.692**	0.582**	1.000	0.665**	0.681**
Compliance Culture	0.659**	0.689**	0.711**	0.681**	0.617**	0.665**	1.000	0.658**
Fairness & Consistency	0.667**	0.706**	0.699**	0.734**	0.633**	0.681**	0.658**	1.000

Note: $p < 0.01$ (two-tailed), indicating all relationships are statistically significant.

Source: Researchers' Computation (SPSS Version 25.0 Output, 2026)

The correlation matrix presented in Table 17 reveals that all the study variables are positively and statistically significant at the 1% level ($p < 0.01$), indicating that improvements in employee discipline are consistently associated with enhanced organizational productivity. Specifically, Corrective Discipline and Employee performance and output exhibit the strongest positive relationship ($r = 0.741$), suggesting that the timely and appropriate application of disciplinary measures substantially improves employee performance, accountability, and the quality of work within the civil service. Similarly, Fairness and Consistency in Disciplinary Administration show a strong positive correlation with Employee Commitment ($r = 0.734$), implying that equitable and transparent disciplinary practices foster greater trust, higher morale, and stronger organizational loyalty among employees.

Furthermore, Employee Compliance Culture is strongly correlated with Goal Achievement ($r = 0.711$), demonstrating that voluntary compliance with organizational rules and ethical standards promotes effective coordination and facilitates the realization of institutional objectives. In the same vein, Preventive Discipline has a strong positive association with Efficiency of Service Delivery ($r = 0.693$), indicating that proactive disciplinary approaches, including effective supervision, clear communication, employee orientation, and ethics training, contribute significantly to improved service efficiency and responsiveness.

Overall, the correlation analysis supports the theoretical proposition that employee discipline is a critical driver of organizational productivity in the Edo State Civil Service. The positive and statistically significant relationships

across all dimensions confirm that stronger disciplinary practices are associated with better employee performance, increased commitment, enhanced service delivery, and improved achievement of organizational goals.

Multiple Regression Analysis

Table 18: Regression Model Summary

Table 18: Regression Model Summary

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Std. Error of Estimate
1	.842	.709	0.702	0.435

Source: Researchers' Computation (SPSS Version 25.0 Output, 2025)

The multiple correlation coefficient ($R = 0.842$) demonstrates a strong positive association between the combined dimensions of employee discipline and organizational productivity. The coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.709$) indicates that approximately 70.9% of the variation in organizational productivity is explained by the collective influence of preventive discipline, corrective discipline, employee compliance culture, and fairness and consistency in disciplinary administration. Furthermore, the Adjusted R^2 value of 0.702 confirms the stability and reliability of the regression model, suggesting that the explanatory power of the model is not substantially affected by sample size or multicollinearity among the independent variables. Overall, these findings imply that employee discipline is a major determinant of organizational productivity, accounting for most of the observed differences in performance across ministries and departments within the Edo State Civil Service.

Table 19: Regression Coefficients

Table 19: Regression Coefficients

Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients (β)	Standard Error	Standardized Coefficients (Beta)	t-value	Sig. (p-value)
(Constant)	1.094	0.292	–	3.75	0.000
Preventive Discipline	0.247	0.068	0.237	3.63	0.001
Corrective Discipline	0.338	0.074	0.324	4.45	0.000
Employee Compliance Culture	0.285	0.070	0.273	4.09	0.000
Fairness & Consistency	0.312	0.071	0.297	4.34	0.000

Source: Researchers' Computation (SPSS Version 25.0 Output, 2025)

All four explanatory variables are statistically significant at the 1% significance level ($p < 0.01$), indicating that each makes a meaningful contribution to organizational productivity. Among them, Corrective Discipline ($\beta = 0.338$, $p = 0.000$) exerts the greatest influence, suggesting that the consistent application of timely and proportionate disciplinary measures enhances employee performance, accountability, and alignment with organizational objectives. Fairness and Consistency in Disciplinary Administration ($\beta = 0.312$, $p = 0.000$) represents the second strongest predictor, implying that impartial, transparent, and consistently applied disciplinary procedures promote employee trust, commitment, and organizational loyalty. Similarly, Employee Compliance Culture ($\beta = 0.285$, $p = 0.000$) demonstrates a significant positive effect, indicating that employees' voluntary adherence to organizational rules, policies, and ethical standards contributes to sustained improvements in productivity. Although Preventive Discipline ($\beta = 0.247$, $p = 0.001$) exhibits the smallest standardized coefficient among the predictors, it remains statistically significant, highlighting the importance of proactive measures such as effective supervision, employee orientation, and ethics training in preventing misconduct and supporting operational efficiency.

Table 20: Hypothesis Testing Summary

Hypothesis	Statement	Decision	Conclusion
H ₀₁	Preventive discipline has no significant effect on efficiency of service delivery.	The rule hypothesis was researched alternative hypothesis upheld	Preventive discipline significantly enhances efficiency of service delivery.
H ₀₂	Corrective discipline has no significant effect on employee performance and output.	The rule hypothesis was researched alternative hypothesis upheld	Corrective discipline significantly improves performance and output.
H ₀₃	Employee compliance culture has no significant effect on goal achievement.	The rule hypothesis was researched alternative hypothesis upheld	Compliance culture significantly enhances goal achievement.
H ₀₄	Fairness and consistency in disciplinary administration have no significant effect on employee commitment.	The rule hypothesis was researched alternative hypothesis upheld	Fairness and consistency significantly increase employee commitment.

Source: Researchers' Computation (SPSS Version 25.0 Output, 2025)

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Preventive Discipline and Efficiency of Service Delivery

The findings revealed that preventive discipline has a significant positive effect on efficiency of service delivery. The finding is in agreement with Gabriel and Zeb-Obipi, 2019 cited in Tamunomiebi and Emeh, 2023 which found prevention discipline focuses at educating employees together with the aim of bringing them together with expected behaviour and cooperation to rules within the organisation.

The result aligns with Goal-Setting Theory (Locke and Lathan, 2002), which posits that when organizations establish clear behavioral expectations and provide preventive guidance, employees are more likely to perform in ways that achieve organizational targets. Similarly, The finding is strongly supported by goal setting theory (locke and lathan, 1980) in field experiment which note that goal enhances employee behavioral compliance and reduce indiscipline and Efficiency (better output with fewer resources) and service delivery (higher quality and consistency).

Corrective Discipline and Employee Performance and Output

Corrective discipline demonstrated the strongest positive effect on employee performance and output. The findings corresponds with Reinforcement Theory, of Skimer (1953) which emphasizes that behavior is shaped by its consequences. When negative behaviors are appropriately sanctioned, and corrective actions are implemented transparently, employees are more likely to adjust their conduct to align with organizational expectations. It also reflects aspects of Equity Theory (Adams, 1963), which perceived fairness in disciplinary actions enhances motivation and performance. The finding is also supported by Adam(1968) studies which found that employees who feel under reward showed poor discipline, how commitment and reduce output, and absentees and employees his perceive fairness show higher productivity, stronger rule compliance and better organizational behavior.

The findings corroborate the work of Ezeani (2022) which found that corrective discipline enhances performance by instilling accountability and responsibility among public employees. Similarly,

Employee Compliance Culture and Goal Achievement

The results revealed that employee compliance culture has a significant and positive effect on goal achievement

The findings is consisted with goal-setting theory of Edwin, lucke and Gary P, Lathan in 1980 which says that specific, clear and challenging goals influence employee behavior and performance. When applied in organization it help build a compliance oriented culture that support goal achievement which ultimately lead to increase productivity. When employees voluntarily comply with organizational standards, goals are achieved more efficiently due to reduced supervision costs and improved cooperation. Compliance culture represents a deeper form of discipline one that originates from intrinsic values rather than external control.

Fairness and Consistency in Disciplinary Administration on Employee Commitment

The study found that fairness and consistency in disciplinary administration significantly influence employee commitment. This result is supported by Equity Theory (Adams, 1963) and Organizational Justice Theory (Greenberg, 1990), which assert that perceived fairness in organizational processes strengthens commitment and job satisfaction. Fairness and consistency reduce perceptions of bias or favoritism, making employees feel valued and respected, which enhances their psychological contract with the organization.

Empirical evidence from Okolie and Osagie (2021) and Ezeani (2018) confirms that fairness in disciplinary administration directly correlates with employee morale and long-term retention in public service organizations. Ogunleye et al. (2020) also noted that perceived fairness improves cooperation, reduces turnover intentions, and strengthens organizational trust.

CONCLUSIONS

Employee discipline is a control mechanism in enhancing organizational productivity. A disciplined workforce guided by preventive, corrective, and compliance-oriented mechanisms, plays a vital role in ensuring efficiency, accountability, and institutional goal attainment. Preventive discipline, equips employees with the ethical foundation and awareness needed to avoid misconduct. Corrective discipline ensures behavioral rectification and reinforces accountability. A strong compliance culture motivates employees to adhere to established standards voluntarily, while fairness and consistency in disciplinary administration build trust and commitment among staff. These elements collectively establish a disciplined organizational climate characterized by punctuality, efficiency, improved output, and loyalty. The study affirms that when discipline is perceived as fair, transparent, and consistent, it fosters a positive work environment that enhances employee morale and organizational performance.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations were proposed:

- i. Organisations should strengthen preventive mechanisms through continuous ethics training, induction, and supervisory programs. Clear communication of rules and behavioral expectations will reduce cases of indiscipline and enhance service efficiency.
- ii. Management of organisations should adopt a feedback-based corrective system that balances fairness with firmness to sustain employee confidence and performance.
- iii. Management should foster a compliance-driven culture by modeling ethical leadership, recognizing compliant employees, and integrating ethics into performance appraisals.
- iv. Employee discipline should be incorporated into the civil services' human resource management strategy. This includes linking disciplinary compliance to promotions, rewards, and performance assessments.
- v. Ministries and departments should adopt performance tracking tools to monitor adherence to rules, punctuality, and productivity.
- vi. Future studies could expand the scope beyond the Edo State Civil Service to include other states or sectors, employ longitudinal data to examine the long-term impact of discipline, or incorporate qualitative methods to gain deeper insights into employee perceptions.

REFERENCES

- Adams, J. S. (1963). Toward an understanding of inequity. *Journal of Abnormal and Social Psychology*, 67(5), 422–436. <https://doi.org/10.1037/h0040968>
- Adamu, S. A., Musa, I. M., & Ali, R. B. (2025). Organizational justice and employee compliance behavior in Nigerian public institutions. *International Journal of Public Administration*, 48(2), 134–150.
- Adebayo A. A, Ojo J. A. and Olanyan O. (2022). The role of audits in enhancing ethical standards in public service delivery *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory* 32 (1), 45-67
- Adebayo A. A, Ojo J. A. and Olanyan O. (2022). The role of audits in enhancing ethical standards in public service delivery *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory* 32 (1), 45-67
- Adebayo, A. O. (2019). *Public service discipline and administrative effectiveness in Nigeria*. Ibadan, Nigeria: Spectrum Books Limited.
- Agbeyinka I. Y. (2024) The impact of Employee Discipline on organizational performance *International Journal of Social and Educational Innovation* volume 11 issue 22,
- Agu, O. L., & Anih, C. E. (2023). Employee discipline and organizational effectiveness in public sector organizations in Nigeria. *International Journal of Human Resource Studies*, 13(2), 45–62. <https://doi.org/10.5296/ijhrs.v13i2.20941>
- Amuewhule, B. I. and Nukan-Adebayo R. T. (2019): Perceived influence of students' indiscipline in academic performance in senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. *The International Journal of Innovative Psychology and Social Development*. 7 (4), 43 - 52
- Chepkoech H. and Minja D. (2026). Compliance with ethical standards by civil servants and the effectiveness of public service delivery in the context of the government of Bimot country (Kenya, East Africa *Jonah of Business and Economics* 9 (1), 10-22
- Chepkoech H. and Minja D. (2026). Compliance with ethical standards by civil servants and the effectiveness of public service delivery in the context of the government of Bimot country (Kenya, East Africa *Jonah of Business and Economics* 9 (1), 10-22.
- Choudharys' and Rana, V. (202) a study on effective Employee Discipline Management in Organizations. *International Journal of Innovation Research in Technology* 9 (6) 271 - 280
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2014). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (5th ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.
- Dehotman K (2023) Relation of work discipline and employee performance. *International Journal of Applied Management and Business* 20 (20) 61-66
- Dessler, G. (2020). *Human resource management* (16th ed.). Harlow, England: Pearson Education Limited.
- Dumisan, E. M. (2002) Impact of Discipline on learning performance M.Sc Thesis-Department of Foundation For Education (unpublished)
- Dumusan E. M. (2002) impact of discipline on learner performance. A thesis submitted in partial requirements for the press of Masters of education in department of foundation for education (unpublished)

- Edo State Civil Service Commission. (2022). Annual report on civil service reforms and workforce performance. Benin City, Nigeria: Edo State Government Press.
- Edo State Civil Service Commission. (2023). Staff strength and administrative records. Benin City, Nigeria: Edo State Government Press.
- Ejumudo, T F. Akpubi, R O. and Ejumudo, K.B.O (2025) Discipline and employee productivity in the Delta state civil service. *Journal of scientific and legal studies, North Eastern University, Gombe (Formerly Pen Resources University, Gombe)* 1 (1), 58 - 81
- Erimife J. A. and Iduozee I. (2025) Employee discipline and organisational performance; A study of non-teaching staff of University of Benin, *LASU Journal of Employee Relation and Human Resource Management* 5 (1) 148 - 160
- Ewale S. J, Tijani A. A, Eyinade M, and Adebajo K. A, (2026) Employee Discipline on organisational performance. In *Touchmate West African Limited Ogba, Lagos State, Nigeria. Umaru Musa Yars Adua University Journal of Business Administration and Management* 2 (1) 322 - 335
- Ezeani, E. O. (2022). *Public administration in Nigeria: Nature Principles and Application* (2nd ed.). Enugu, Nigeria: Zik-Chuks Publishers.
- Gee-Jung, K and Wong A. (2017) Employees commitments and its impact on organizational performance *Asian Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting* 5 (2), 1 -12
- Goldstean S. M, Johnston R., Duffy, J. and Rao, J. (2012). The service concept: the missing link in service design research? *Journal of Operations Management* 20, 121-134
- Greenberg, J. (1990). Organizational justice: Yesterday, today, and tomorrow. *Journal of Management*, 16(2), 399–432. <https://doi.org/10.1177/014920639001600208>
- Ibrahim H. A and Yakubu M. M. (2019) Effect of organizational ethics on service delivery of employees in the public sectors: Nigerian perspective, *European journal of Business and Management* 11 (36), 154- 161
- Idris S. D. and Alegbeleye G. I. (2015) discipline and organizational effectiveness: a study of Ni service review of public administration and management 4 (3) 88 - 107
- Ishiaka A. S. (2025) Assessing the impact of employee discipline in organizational survival: The human resources management perspective. *Journal of Human, Social And Political Science Research* 7. 197 - 280
- Katz, D., & Kahn, R. L. (2018). *The social psychology* New York: John Wiley and sons
- Khan H, Razi A. Ali S. A. Asghar A. (2013) A Study on relationship between organisation job commitment and its determination among CSRS and management level employee of Pakistan (Telecommunication sector) *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research* 3 (11) 284-369
- Kothari, C. R., & Garg, G. (2019). *Research methodology: Methods and techniques* (4th ed.). New Delhi, India: New Age International Publishers.
- Lee C. and Ches C. (2013) The relationship between employee commitment and job attitude and its effect on service quality in the tourism industry. *American Journal of Industrial and Business Management* 3; 196-208
- Lock, E. A. and Lathan G. P. (2002) building a practical useful goal setting and task motivation: a 35 years Odyssey *American Psychology* 52 (9) 705- 717
- Masrui, A. M. and Permane A. I. (2025) The effect of motivation, work environment and discipline on employee productivity *PT. ABC Maneggio* 2 (4) 23-35
- Meyer, J. P., & Allen, N. J. (1991). A three-component conceptualization of organizational commitment. *Human Resource Management Review*, 1(1), 61–89. [https://doi.org/10.1016/1053-4822\(91\)90011-Z](https://doi.org/10.1016/1053-4822(91)90011-Z)
- Obiagheli O. H. Uzochukwu O. C. and Chukwuemeke, D. N. (2015) Work life balance and employee performance in selected commercial banks in lagos state. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Management Sciences* 3; 69-76
- Ogunleye, A. J., Adebayo, O. A., & Ayinde, I. A. (2020). Human capital development and organizational productivity in the Nigerian public service. *International Journal of Public Administration and Management Research*, 5(3), 45–58.
- Ogunleye, A. J., Adebayo, O. I., & Ayinde, O. A. (2020). Employee discipline and productivity in public sector organizations in Nigeria. *Journal of Public Administration and Governance*, 10(3), 89–104. <https://doi.org/10.5296/jpag.v10i3.17644>
- Ogunleye, A. J., Adebayo, O. I., & Odusami, K. T. (2020). Public service discipline and service delivery effectiveness in Nigeria. *International Journal of Management Research*, 7(2), 52–68.
- Okoli, C. C. and Emebo O. S. (2026) Workplace Discipline and service delivery in Anambra state local government system *International Journal of Public Administration (IJOPAD)* 5 (1); 120 - 138

- Okolie, U. C., & Osagie, R. O. (2021). *Organizational behaviour in the public sector*. Benin City, Nigeria: Mindex Publishing.
- Okpiabhele, E. Aroaye I. C and Oladimeji, S. B. (2025) Employee discipline management and organisational performance of deposit money banks in Ondo town Ondo state. *International Journal of Resreach* 12 (1) 858 - 876
- Omoregie, O. (2022). Progressive discipline and employee behavior management in Nigerian public service. *Nigerian Journal of Management Sciences*, 9(2), 55–70.
- Prasetya A, Kato M. (2011) the effect of finance and non--financial compensation to the employee performance. *The 2nd international research symolum in service management*. Yoghakarta, Indonesia
- Robbins, S. P., & Judge, T. A. (2013). *Organizational behavior* (15th ed.). chall River, Pearson Education.
- Skinner, B. F. (1953). *Science and human behavior*. New York, NY: Macmillan.
- Sutrisno E. (2019) *Manasemen Sumber Daya Manusia*, Jakarta, Penerbit P T kencana Sinabela L. P. (2016) *Manasemen Sumber daya Manusia; Membangun Tim Kirja Yang Soli Untuk Meningkatkan Kinerja*, Jakarta; Bumi Aksara
- Tamunimiebi M. D. and Emeh N. K. (2023) Workplace discipline and organizational effectiveness. A conceptual research. *The strategic journal of Business and change management* 10 (1), 304 - 314.
- Tamunosiki-Amadi I. O, Timi M. E and Dogitimiye M. (2020) Employee involvement and organisational productivity in the Beyelsa State Banking sector SSRG *International Journal of Economics and Management studies* 7 (2), 160 - 168
- Taro, Y, (1967) *Statistics an introductory analysis* (2nd end) Harper and Row
- Taylor, F. W. (1911). *The principles of scientific management*. New York, NY: Harper & Brothers.
- Udofia A. N, and Asue S. A. (2023) discipline and personnel performance in an organization. Retrieved on 16 May 2026 from: <https://www.researchgate.com>
- Wang H.Q,Li X.Y and Liu, J. P. (2023). Effective goal conflict and academic success. Developing consistent habits for goal attainment *Journal of Academic Motivation* 34 (2) 142-157
- Mangkunegare A. A. (2011) *Manajemen Sumber Dayo Manusia Perusahaan*, Remaja Rosdakarya
- Wibowo L. (2007) *Performance Management* (2nd ed) PT. Raja Grafindo Persada